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Skills Enhancer, Floor Raiser, or Gap Closer? Pre-Primary Education Expansion and Reading Achievement in Comparative Perspective

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Abstract

This article examines whether the expansion of pre-primary education functions as a skills enhancer, a floor raiser, or a gap closer in later educational achievement. Drawing on five waves of PIRLS data from 2001 to 2021, covering around 700,000 fourth-grade students in 43 countries, the study analyses the association between national pre-primary participation rates and three country-year outcomes: average reading achievement, educational poverty, and achievement gaps by parental education. Using a two-step multilevel meta-regression strategy, the analysis distinguishes cross-national differences from within-country change over time. The findings show that higher pre-primary participation is consistently associated with higher average reading scores and lower shares of students below the PIRLS low benchmark. By contrast, the association with socioeconomic achievement gaps is weaker and more conditional. Exploratory analyses suggest that this limited gap-closing role reflects persistent social inequalities in access to pre-primary education and unequal returns to attendance. Further analyses for European countries indicate that the equalizing potential of expansion is stronger where participation is accompanied by higher expenditure per child. The article contributes to debates on social investment by showing that early education expansion may raise overall competencies and reduce low achievement more readily than it transforms relative inequalities.

1. Introduction

Over the last two decades, pre-primary education for children aged 3–5, the stage immediately preceding compulsory schooling, has become a central component of the social investment paradigm. Rather than intervening only after disadvantage has emerged, social investment approaches emphasize policies that strengthen capabilities early in the life course, with the expectation that timely intervention can improve later outcomes and reduce the reproduction of inequality (Morel et al., 2012; Hemerijck, 2017). Pre-primary education occupies a privileged place in this perspective because it is expected to support children’s development, facilitate parental employment, and mitigate inequalities before they become entrenched (European Commission, 2011).

This policy prominence reflects a basic sociological insight: educational inequality begins well before formal schooling (Blossfeld et al. 2017). Children enter school with unequal language exposure, cognitive stimulation, routines, and cultural resources, and these early differences often shape later achievement trajectories (Bradbury et al. 2015). Research across economics, psychology, and sociology has shown that learning is cumulative: early competencies facilitate later learning, whereas early deficits often persist or widen over time (Heckman, 2006; Melhuish et al., 2015). Families with higher levels of education and material resources are generally better able to provide cognitively rich environments and structured developmental support, while disadvantaged families face greater constraints in doing so (Kulic et al., 2019). In this context, pre-primary education may alter the relationship between family background and early skill formation by offering structured learning environments, language-rich interactions, and developmental support outside the household (Raudenbush & Eschmann, 2015; Burger, 2010; Schmutz, 2024). If sufficiently accessible and adequately resourced, it may partially standardize the conditions under which children enter school (Esping-Andersen et al., 2012).

Yet this is also where a broader debate on social investment becomes relevant. Although early intervention is often presented as an egalitarian strategy, its distributive consequences are not self-evident (Raudenbush & Eschmann, 2015). A large literature documents positive effects of early childhood education at the individual level, often showing that disadvantaged children benefit at least as much as, and sometimes more than, advantaged children (Kulic et al., 2019; Van Huizen & Plantenga, 2018; Schmutz, 2024). Research on specific reforms likewise suggests that expansions in access can improve later educational outcomes under favorable institutional conditions (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011; Felfe & Lalive, 2018). However, comparative evidence remains more limited on whether the expansion of pre-primary education within countries over time is associated with better later outcomes among subsequent cohorts, and whether such associations are more visible in overall achievement, in the reduction of low performance, or in the narrowing of socioeconomic gaps. Much cross-national research still relies on static country differences or on individual-level comparisons that do not clearly

distinguish the effects of educational expansion from stable contextual differences (Dämmrich & Esping-Andersen, 2017; Cebolla-Boado et al., 2017).

As a result, we still know relatively little about whether expanding pre-primary participation changes the distribution of educational outcomes within countries over time. Social investment policies have the potential to enhance average capabilities, reduce the risk of poor outcomes, and weaken socioeconomic inequalities, but whether they can simultaneously achieve all these goals remains an open question (Morel et al., 2012; Hemerijck, 2017). Recent comparative work on ECE policy documents further suggests that early childhood reforms are often framed more strongly around individual achievement and competitiveness than around cohesion or structural equalization (Bobrowicz et al., 2025). In the case of pre-primary education, this means that wider participation may improve children's competence levels and reduce low performance, while its capacity to narrow socioeconomic differences may be more context-dependent (Esping-Andersen et al., 2012; Kulic et al., 2019). For this reason, we argue it is useful to distinguish between three possible functions of pre-primary expansion: enhancing skills, raising the floor, and closing social gaps.

This article addresses this issue by examining the expansion of pre-primary education for ages 3–5 and its association with children's later reading outcomes. We focus on three analytically distinct dimensions: average reading achievement, educational poverty, and achievement inequalities within countries, especially those linked to parental education. We also examine whether these associations are stronger when expansion is accompanied by higher investment in pre-primary provision, on the assumption that access and quality are intertwined and that expansion should matter more where institutional resources are greater. Empirically, we draw on the five available waves of the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS), covering about 700,000 students in 43 countries over two decades.

Our contribution is threefold. First, we provide longitudinal comparative evidence on the relationship between pre-primary expansion and children's later reading outcomes across a large and diverse set of countries over two decades. Second, we show that pre-primary expansion does not operate uniformly across outcomes: it may function as a skills enhancer, a floor raiser, and a gap closer, but these three functions do not necessarily coincide empirically. Third, by examining whether the benefits of expansion are stronger under higher levels of investment, we bring institutional heterogeneity more directly into the analysis. In doing so, the paper speaks not only to research on early childhood education, but also to a broader sociological debate on the promises and limits of social investment: whether policies that intervene early in the life course primarily improve overall capabilities, protect those at the bottom, or genuinely alter the distribution of advantage.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Pre-primary education as a skills enhancer

A first and most widely recognized function of pre-primary education is that of a skills enhancer. The core idea is that participation in organized educational settings before compulsory schooling can strengthen children's cognitive and linguistic development and thereby improve later academic performance (Bradbury et al., 2015). This expectation is rooted in the literature on cumulative skill formation, which shows that early competencies facilitate later learning, while early deficits often persist or widen over time (Heckman, 2006). From a sociological perspective, this skills-enhancing role stems from the capacity of pre-primary education to institutionalize learning experiences at an early stage of the life course (Esping-Andersen, 2008). While families remain central in shaping children's development, formal pre-primary settings expose children to structured pedagogical activities, adult-child interactions, peer learning, and routines that are less dependent on the resources and practices of individual households (Kulic et al., 2019). In this sense, pre-primary education may function as an early extension of the educational system, raising the baseline level of school readiness within cohorts (Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

At the macro level, this implies that broader participation in pre-primary education should be associated with higher later achievement among subsequent cohorts. This interpretation is consistent with the broader social investment perspective, which treats early childhood policies as investments in human capabilities designed to generate later returns (Morel et al., 2012; Hemerijck, 2017). Empirical evidence broadly supports this view. Reviews and meta-analyses generally find positive effects of early childhood education on later cognitive development, especially in literacy and language-related domains (Burger, 2010; Kulic et al., 2019; Van Huizen & Plantenga, 2018). Evidence from specific reforms points in the same direction: the Norwegian expansion of subsidized childcare generated positive long-term educational and labor-market consequences (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011), while studies from other contexts, such as Spain and Germany, also show benefits of broader access for later academic achievement (Felfe & Lalive, 2018). Although most of this literature focuses on individual participation or specific reform episodes, it strongly suggests that exposure to pre-primary education can improve later competence development. Building on this literature, our first expectation is as follows.

H1. Pre-primary education as a skills enhancer: higher levels of participation in pre-primary education are associated with higher average reading achievement in later cohorts.

2.2 Pre-primary education as a floor raiser

A second function of pre-primary education is that of a floor raiser. Whereas the first function concerns average achievement, this second one concerns the lower tail of the performance distribution. The key question is not only whether broader access raises mean performance,

but whether it reduces educational poverty, that is, the proportion of children performing below a basic proficiency threshold.

The theoretical logic is again rooted in cumulative skill formation, but here the emphasis is on children who enter school with fewer prior learning opportunities. Before compulsory schooling, children differ substantially in the cognitive stimulation, linguistic exposure, and developmental support they experience. According to the counterfactual model of learning, school and pre-school institutions can either reproduce or reduce such differences depending on whether they compensate for deficits in prior learning opportunities (Raudenbush & Eschmann, 2015). In this sense, pre-primary education may raise the minimum level of competence with which children enter school by providing structured learning experiences, language-rich interactions, and developmental support before school entry (Esping-Andersen et al., 2012; Burger, 2010; Schmutz, 2024). Although children from socioeconomically disadvantaged families are often more likely to benefit, the floor-raising function is not limited to them alone; it concerns more broadly those at greater risk of weak early skill development and later low performance.

In sociological terms, this function matters because it connects early education to the prevention of educational marginalization. A policy may have limited effects on relative inequalities between social groups while still playing an important role in reducing the prevalence of very low achievement.

Existing empirical evidence is broadly consistent with this interpretation. Many studies conclude that early childhood education often yields especially strong gains among children with fewer prior learning resources, particularly when access is broad and program quality is adequate (Van Huizen & Plantenga, 2018; Kulic et al., 2019; Schmutz, 2024). Studies of universal or large-scale expansion also suggest that early education can reduce later risks of weak academic performance and social exclusion (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011; Felfe & Lalive, 2018), while cross-national work associates more encompassing and better-developed early education systems with lower educational disadvantage, even if the mechanisms remain contested (Dämmrich & Esping-Andersen, 2017).

Taken together, this literature suggests that the consequences of pre-primary expansion may be especially visible at the bottom of the achievement distribution. If so, countries that expand participation should not only display higher mean reading performance, but also a smaller share of students who fail to reach basic levels of literacy proficiency. In this sense, pre-primary expansion may function as a floor-raising reform by reducing the prevalence of very low achievement. This leads to our second hypothesis.

H2. Pre-primary education as a floor raiser: higher levels of participation in pre-primary education are associated with lower educational poverty, measured as the share of students performing below a basic proficiency threshold.

2.3 Pre-primary education as a gap closer

A third function of pre-primary education is that of a gap closer, which refers to whether broader participation not only improves achievement overall and reduces low performance, but also narrows socioeconomic differences in achievement within countries. This is the strongest equalizing claim often associated with early childhood policies and with the social investment paradigm more generally: that intervening early can weaken the relationship between family background and later educational outcomes.

The theoretical case for this expectation is strong. Because family environments differ so markedly in cultural capital, educational practices, and material resources, organized early education may reduce the extent to which children's skill development depends on their social origins. If disadvantaged children gain proportionally more from access to high-quality pre-primary education than advantaged children, expansion may reduce socioeconomic inequalities already before school entry and, through this mechanism, weaken later achievement gaps by parental education or other indicators of social origin (Burger, 2010; Esping-Andersen et al., 2012; Raudenbush & Eschmann, 2015).

At the same time, the gap-closing function is theoretically more uncertain than the other two. For expansion to reduce later inequalities, two conditions are especially important. First, rising participation must reduce the socioeconomic gap in access to pre-primary education. This cannot be taken for granted. If participation rises in parallel across social groups, or even more strongly among advantaged families, expansion may leave the social distribution of early educational exposure largely unchanged. This is particularly plausible where access to early childhood services remains socially stratified and shaped by policy design (Van Lancker & Ghysels, 2016; Pavolini & Van Lancker, 2018).

Second, attendance must not generate systematically larger benefits for already advantaged children. Even if expansion broadens access, the gap-closing potential of pre-primary education will remain limited if higher-SES children are better able to convert attendance into later academic performance. This may occur because more advantaged families secure access to better-resourced pre-primary settings, or because children differ in their responsiveness to the same educational experience. In line with cumulative skill formation, children who enter pre-primary education with stronger prior learning conditions may be better positioned to capitalize on it, so that "learning begets learning" even within early educational institutions (Heckman, 2006). As a result, pre-primary expansion may raise competence broadly and even reduce educational poverty without proportionally transforming socioeconomic gaps.

Empirical evidence reflects this ambiguity. Reviews of individual-level studies frequently find stronger benefits of early education among disadvantaged children, suggesting equalizing potential (Kulic et al., 2019; Schmutz, 2024). Cross-national analyses have also argued that early childhood education can mitigate inequalities in achievement, particularly in contexts of broad and high-quality provision (Cebolla-Boado et al., 2017; Dämmrich & Esping-Andersen,

2017). Yet the evidence is far from uniform. Some studies show that inequalities in participation and quality can limit equalizing effects, and that early intervention often improves overall performance more clearly than it alters relative social differences (Van Lancker & Pavolini, 2023; Schoenholzer & Burger, 2024). Empirical evidence also suggests that the equalizing potential of preschool is historically and institutionally contingent. In a long-run study of Spain, Cebolla-Boado and Manzano (2025) show that preschool contributed more clearly to educational equality when access became less selective, implying that early education has not always functioned as an equalizing investment to the same extent.

Taken together, this literature suggests that the gap-closing function of pre-primary expansion should be treated as plausible but more conditional than the skills-enhancing and floor-raising functions. Accordingly, we formulate our third hypothesis as follows.

H3. Pre-primary education as a gap closer: higher levels of participation in pre-primary education are associated with smaller socioeconomic achievement gaps, although these associations are expected to be weaker and less consistent than those for average achievement and educational poverty.

Related to this hypothesis, we also examine two potential micro-level mechanisms: unequal participation in pre-primary education across socioeconomic groups and unequal returns to pre-primary participation in terms of later reading achievement.

2.4 Heterogeneous effects of pre-primary expansion: the role of investment and quality

The three functions outlined above should not be expected to operate uniformly across contexts. Expansion in participation is not a homogeneous institutional process. Countries differ not only in the timing and pace of expansion, but also in the resources, governance arrangements, staff qualifications, and pedagogical conditions under which pre-primary education is delivered (Blossfeld et al., 2017). Comparative evidence consistently shows substantial cross-national heterogeneity in the quality and organization of early childhood systems, including staff-child ratios, workforce professionalization, and public expenditure levels (OECD, 2017, 2020, 2025). This implies that similar increases in participation may have different consequences depending on how expansion is implemented.

This matters because the consequences of pre-primary expansion depend not simply on access, but on what children actually experience in settings (Gambaro et al., 2014). Research commonly distinguishes between structural quality—such as staff qualifications, child-staff ratios, and group size—and process quality, namely the quality of daily interactions and learning experiences, with the latter particularly important for child development and partly shaped by the former (OECD, 2019; von Suchodoletz et al., 2023). Expansion without adequate resources may therefore dilute quality by increasing enrolment faster than institutional capacity, whereas expansion accompanied by stronger investment is more likely to sustain the conditions under which participation yields developmental benefits (OECD, 2025). Access and

quality should thus be treated as intertwined dimensions of institutional expansion rather than as separate phenomena.

This argument is especially important from a comparative perspective. Countries that expanded pre-primary education from already institutionalized and well-funded systems may derive different benefits than countries where expansion occurred more recently or under tighter fiscal and organizational constraints. The same increase in enrolment may therefore have stronger consequences in contexts where institutional capacity is sufficient to sustain quality. This point also links the present study back to debates on social investment: investing early is not only a matter of extending access, but also of ensuring that expanded provision can produce substantive developmental benefits (Gambaro et al., 2014).

Empirical literature strongly supports the importance of quality. Reviews of early childhood research repeatedly conclude that the effects of attendance depend crucially on structural and process quality, including staff qualifications, educational content, and adult-child interactions (Pianta et al., 2009; Melhuish et al., 2015; OECD, 2019). Cross-national work similarly suggests that more generous, universal, and better-developed systems have greater equalizing potential than systems marked by weaker or more stratified provision (Dämmrich & Esping-Andersen, 2017; Schoenholzer & Burger, 2024). This indicates that the consequences of pre-primary expansion should not be inferred from participation rates alone. For this reason, we develop out fourth hypothesis as follows.

H4. Heterogeneous effects by investment/quality: the positive associations between pre-primary expansion and later educational outcomes are expected to be stronger where rising participation is accompanied by higher investment in pre-primary provision.

3. Analytical strategy

3.1 Data

This study uses data from the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS), a large-scale international assessment of fourth-grade students conducted every five years since 2001. We harmonize the five available waves—2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, and 2021—to build a repeated cross-sectional dataset for analysing cross-national differences and within-country change over time. PIRLS is well suited to this study because it combines internationally comparable reading scores with parental information on children’s early educational experiences, including pre-primary attendance before compulsory schooling. Although retrospective, these reports refer to relatively recent experiences, as PIRLS assesses children in fourth grade, and similar measures have been used in previous comparative research on early education and later achievement (e.g. Cebolla-Boado et al., 2017).

The analytical sample includes countries observed in at least two PIRLS rounds and excludes country-year units with substantial missingness on key variables. It covers about 700,000

students from 43 countries across 143 country-year units, spanning Europe, Asia, the Middle East and North Africa, and the Americas. This broad coverage allows us to examine pre-primary expansion beyond a narrow Western or high-income perspective. PIRLS provides nationally representative student samples and sampling weights, which we use in the analyses. We also combine the microdata with time-varying macro-level indicators from international sources, including UNESCO and World Bank databases, to measure national educational, demographic, and socioeconomic conditions. Further details on sampling, country coverage, and data sources are reported in the Appendix A.

3.2 Outcomes, main predictor and moderator

To capture the different ways in which pre-primary expansion may matter for later educational outcomes, we distinguish between three dimensions of reading performance at the country-year level. These correspond to the three functions discussed in the theoretical framework: skill enhancement, floor raising, and gap closing.

The first outcome is *average reading achievement*, measured as the mean PIRLS reading score in each country and year. This captures whether pre-primary expansion acts as a skills enhancer by raising the overall level of later competencies. Reading performance is measured through five plausible values, which account for the uncertainty arising from PIRLS's matrix-sampling design, where each student answers only a subset of the assessment items. Individual scores range from approximately 247 to around 676 points, with most students scoring between about 300 and 650. The score scale was established in 2001 to ensure comparability across countries and overtime.

The second outcome is *educational poverty*, defined as the proportion of students scoring below 400 points, the lowest international benchmark in PIRLS reporting. Students below this threshold cannot retrieve explicitly stated information or make straightforward inferences from simple texts.¹ This measure captures whether pre-primary expansion functions as a floor raiser by reducing the lower tail of the achievement distribution.

The third outcome is *achievement inequality by parental education*, measured as the average score difference between students with at least one tertiary-educated parent and all other students, controlling for gender and the language spoken at home.² This is our main indicator of whether pre-primary expansion operates as a gap closer by weakening the association between social origin and children's later reading performance. Parental education is especially appropriate here because it captures a key dimension of social origin related to children's learning opportunities at home and can be more readily harmonized across countries than other socioeconomic indicators (Waldfogel et al. 2023). Table B2 in the Appendix summarizes the three outcomes across the five years.

¹ This benchmark is commonly interpreted as signalling basic reading proficiency and therefore offers a substantively meaningful indicator of very poor achievement.

² These variables are included as basic controls for compositional differences in reading performance and pre-primary participation, particularly those related to gender and to exposure to the language of the test.

The key predictor is the *country-year participation rate in pre-primary education*, estimated from the PIRLS parental questionnaire. This measure is based on parental reports of whether the child attended pre-primary education before entering primary school. It is especially useful because it refers to the same cohorts whose reading competencies are later assessed in PIRLS, while the retrospective recall period remains relatively limited given that children are observed in the fourth grade.³ Across the country-year units in our sample, the average estimated participation rate in pre-primary education is about 88 per cent, although levels vary considerably (see Figure B1 in the Appendix for the participation rates by country and year). This distribution is consistent with the idea that countries in the sample are located at different stages of institutionalization and expansion. Moreover, approximately half of the total variance in participation is between countries and half within countries over time (Figure B2 in the Appendix), indicating meaningful temporal variation for longitudinal analysis. To assess the validity of this indicator, we compared the PIRLS-based participation rates with UNESCO administrative estimates and available through the World Bank. The correlation is about 0.85, suggesting that the PIRLS-derived measure captures country-level participation patterns with reasonable accuracy; the full comparison is reported in Figure B3 in the Appendix.

Our key moderator is a proxy for pre-primary quality, measured as expenditure per full-time equivalent student in current US dollars, based on OECD data (see Table A2 in the Appendix for additional details and sources). Because these data are available only for a subset of European countries and only for the most recent cohorts, the analyses including this moderator are based on a smaller sample of 19 countries with students tested in 2016 and 2021. In this sample, average expenditure is around 7,500 US dollars per child, ranging from approximately 4,000 to nearly 15,000 dollars.

3.3 Control variables

To reduce the risk that the association between pre-primary expansion and later reading outcomes reflects differences in cohort composition or broader country-level change, we include a set of time-varying macro-level controls. These capture three domains. First, socioeconomic development is measured through the Human Development Index (HDI), which may affect both educational provision and student performance. Second, social structure and demographic composition are captured by the share of tertiary-educated adults, the share of foreign-born population, and the share of urban population, accounting for differences in adult educational attainment, migration, and the spatial organization of opportunities. Third, the educational and distributive context is captured by the GINI index, expenditure on primary education, and the share of students enrolled in private schools, reflecting income inequality,

³ In the 2001, 2006, and 2011 waves, parents were asked whether their child had attended ISCED level 0 before primary school. In 2016 and 2021, the wording referred more specifically to “a pre-primary educational program for children age 3 or older, including kindergarten,” before first grade. Despite slight wording changes, the questions are substantively comparable and consistently capture attendance in the educational stage preceding compulsory schooling.

investment in the schooling level where outcomes are observed, and cross-national differences in school provision.

These controls account for the fact that pre-primary expansion may coincide with broader changes in development, inequality, demographic composition, or educational investment. While they do not remove all concerns about confounding, they help assess whether the relationship between pre-primary expansion and later outcomes persists net of relevant macro-level processes. Further details on country-level control variable definitions, availability, descriptive statistics, and correlations are reported in Appendix Tables A2, B3, and B4, and Figure B4.

3.4 Methods

To examine whether within-country changes in participation in pre-primary education are associated with changes in later reading outcomes, we use a two-step multilevel meta-regression approach (Van Den Noortgate & Onghena, 2003). This strategy is appropriate because the outcomes of interest—average achievement, educational poverty, and achievement gaps—are defined at the country-year level but must first be estimated from student-level PIRLS data (Vigna, Parente & Triventi, 2026). We summarize the main steps below; further details are reported in Appendix A.

In the first step, we estimate each outcome separately for every country-year using the PIRLS microdata: average reading achievement, educational poverty, and achievement inequality by parental education. This produces, for each country-year, both an outcome estimate and its sampling variance, while accounting for PIRLS sampling weights, plausible values, and error clustering at the school-level.

In the second step, these country-year estimates are used as dependent variables in a set of meta-regression models in which the key predictor is the national pre-primary participation rate. Since repeated country-year observations are nested within countries, we estimate multilevel models that account for this structure and incorporate first-step sampling variance, giving greater weight to more precise estimates.

This approach offers three advantages. First, it allows us to derive substantively meaningful country-year outcomes while fully exploiting the student-level PIRLS data. Second, it respects the complex survey design of PIRLS, including plausible values, weights, and clustered sampling. Third, it allows us to distinguish between cross-national differences and within-country change over time, which is central to our argument.

We estimate three specifications: a baseline model with pre-primary participation and country random intercepts; a second model adding time-varying macro-level controls; and a third further adding country fixed effects, which identifies associations only from within-country changes and absorbs all time-invariant national characteristics.

4. Empirical findings

4.1 Descriptive patterns and trends in pre-primary participation and in the three educational outcomes

We begin by examining the descriptive evolution of participation in pre-primary education across the country-years in our sample. Overall, participation levels are high but far from uniform. Across the 143 country-year units, the average share of students who attended pre-primary education is about 88 per cent, although the distribution remains wide, ranging from approximately 24 to 100 per cent. Western European country-years are often close to universal participation, while countries in other regions show more variable coverage.

Figure 1 shows that pre-primary participation generally expanded between 2001 and 2021, though trajectories vary across countries. Systems with already high participation remained near universal coverage, whereas several countries starting from lower levels experienced marked increases, suggesting partial convergence over time. In most countries, participation trends among children with at least one tertiary-educated parent and those among other children move broadly in parallel, indicating that expansion was often broad-based rather than limited to one social group.

Overall, these trends show meaningful within-country temporal variation alongside substantial cross-national heterogeneity. This is important because the key predictor captures not only stable institutional differences between countries, but also real changes over time within countries. The strong correspondence between PIRLS-based participation rates and UNESCO administrative data further supports the validity of this measure as an indicator of national pre-primary expansion (see Figure B3 in the Appendix).

Substantial cross-country variation is also evident across the three educational outcomes. As shown in Figure 2, average reading scores are highest in East Asian and high-performing European countries, several of which remain above 530 points throughout the study period, and lowest in Middle Eastern and North African countries, where scores often fall below 450 points. Educational poverty follows the opposite pattern: it is lowest in high-performing systems and highest—sometimes above 30 percent—where average performance is lower. The parental education gap is positive in all countries, indicating higher scores among students with at least one tertiary-educated parent, but its size varies considerably, from about 15 points in Hong Kong to 83 points in Morocco. These patterns show substantial variation in both the level and distribution of educational outcomes, providing empirical leverage for the multivariate analyses.

Figure 1. Pre-primary participation trends by country: average participation rate, participation rate of children with highly educated parents, and participation rate of children with low-educated parents.

Figure 2. Estimated educational outcomes by country: average values across years and observed ranges.

4.2 Main associations with achievement, educational poverty, and social gaps

We now turn to the multivariate results to test H1 to H3, focusing on whether the expansion of pre-primary education acts as a skills enhancer, floor raiser, and gap closer. Figure 3 reports the estimated association between pre-primary participation and the three main outcomes under three increasingly demanding specifications: a random-intercept model, a random-intercept model with macro-level controls, and a country fixed-effects model with the same controls (Figure B4 in the Appendix shows the corresponding simple correlations). Overall, the results reveal a clear hierarchy: pre-primary expansion is most consistently associated with average reading achievement and educational poverty, while its association with achievement inequality by parental education is weaker and more conditional.

For average reading achievement, higher pre-primary participation is associated with higher later reading performance across all specifications. A ten-percentage-point increase in participation corresponds to an increase of roughly 5 to 7 PIRLS points, depending on the model. The association remains positive and statistically robust in the fixed-effects specification, which relies only on within-country change over time. This supports the interpretation of pre-primary education as a skills enhancer.

A similarly consistent pattern emerges for educational poverty. Higher pre-primary participation is associated with a lower share of students performing below the PIRLS low benchmark. The coefficients imply that a ten-percentage-point increase in participation reduces educational poverty by about 1.2–1.5 percentage points, corresponding to roughly 9–12% of the average level. This association also remains negative and statistically robust under country fixed effects, supporting the view of pre-primary expansion as a floor raiser.

The evidence is more mixed for achievement gaps by parental education. The association is negative in the more demanding specifications, suggesting some potential for gap closing, but

it is weaker than for the other outcomes. A statistically significant reduction emerges only in the fixed-effects model with controls, where a ten-percentage-point increase in participation reduces the parental education gap by about 2.5 points. Using mother’s education alone—often identified as a strong predictor of children’s educational outcomes (Harding et al., 2015)—produces a similar estimate of around 2 points, although it is not statistically significant (Figure C1 in the Appendix). Thus, while the reduction is not negligible, the evidence is less robust than for average achievement and educational poverty. Pre-primary expansion therefore appears more consistently associated with improving the overall distribution and reducing the lower tail than with narrowing relative inequalities between social groups.

Figure 3. Association between participation rate in pre-primary education (PPE) and the three educational outcomes: regression results from the meta-multilevel models (N countries=43; N country-years= 143).

We assess robustness in two ways. First, we replicate the analysis using the natural logarithm of the pre-primary participation rate (Figure C2 in the Appendix shows the corresponding correlations and Figure C3 the meta-multilevel results). Second, we re-estimate all models on the subset of country-years with complete data on all country-level controls to improve comparability across specifications (Figure C4 in the Appendix). Both checks produce results very similar to the main analysis.

Because the pooled sample of 43 countries may combine very diverse institutional and social contexts, potentially conflating different underlying processes, we also re-estimate the models for European countries only. As shown in Figure 4, the results closely mirror those from the full sample: higher pre-primary participation is associated with a small but significant increase in average performance and a substantial reduction in educational poverty, while the association with socioeconomic inequality remains less robust.

Figure 4. Association between participation rate in pre-primary education (PPE) and the three educational outcomes: regression results from the meta-multilevel models estimated on European countries only (N countries=24; N country-years= 84).

Taken together, these results align closely with the theoretical distinction developed above. Pre-primary expansion appears to operate most clearly as a skills enhancer and floor raiser, while its role as a gap closer is more limited and conditional. This does not mean that social inequalities are unaffected, but rather that reductions in the lower tail of the distribution and improvements in average performance emerge more consistently than the narrowing of differences by parental education.

4.3 Behind the persistence of social gaps

To better understand why rising pre-primary participation does not translate more clearly into narrower socio-economic gaps in achievement, we examine two potential mechanisms operating at the micro-level: unequal participation in pre-primary and unequal returns to pre-primary in terms of later test performance.

First, we assess whether socioeconomic inequalities in pre-primary attendance have declined over time. Although countries generally move toward higher participation, aggregate expansion does not necessarily imply equalization if attendance gaps between social groups remain stable. Figure 5, top panel, tests this within the meta-multilevel framework. The results show that children of highly educated parents are consistently more likely to attend pre-primary education than children of low-educated parents. The estimated gap changes only modestly across cohorts, suggesting substantial stability rather than closure. Thus, even as participation expands, disadvantaged children do not benefit disproportionately from this expansion, limiting its potential to reduce achievement gaps.

The second mechanism points in the same direction. While pre-primary attendance is associated with positive test-score returns for all children, Figure 5, bottom panel, shows that these returns are consistently larger for children of highly educated parents. Across cohorts, the estimated advantage in returns is sizeable, roughly 15 to 25 score points. This suggests that

socioeconomically advantaged children are better positioned to convert pre-primary attendance into later academic performance.

Together, these exploratory findings help explain why pre-primary expansion is only weakly associated with reduced socioeconomic inequality. If advantaged children remain more likely to attend pre-primary education and also derive larger learning benefits from it, broader participation alone is unlikely to generate strong equalizing effects. The limited gap-closing role of pre-primary expansion may therefore reflect persistent stratification in both access and returns.

Figure 5. Advantage of children of highly educated parents over those of low-educated parents (ref.) in the probability of attending pre-primary education (PPE) (top panel) and in the test-score returns to pre-primary attendance (bottom panel).

NOTE: Results are derived from meta-multilevel regression models. In the top graph, we first ran logit models and estimated the difference in the average probability of attending PPE between children of highly educated parents and those of low-educated parents, separately for each country-year unit. We then used these estimates, together with their standard errors, as outcomes in a meta-multilevel regression model with year fixed effects (43 countries; 141 country-year units). In the bottom graph, we first estimated, separately for each country-year unit, the effect of the interaction between parental education and PPE attendance on test scores. These estimates, along with their standard errors, were then used as outcomes in a meta-multilevel regression model with year fixed effects (43 countries; 143 country-year units).

4.4 Heterogeneous patterns by investment in pre-primary education

We finally examine whether the association between pre-primary participation and later outcomes varies by investment in pre-primary provision. Due to data limitations, these analyses are restricted to 19 European countries and the 2016 and 2021 cohorts.

Table 1 reports meta-multilevel models predicting the three outcomes through the interaction between pre-primary participation and pre-primary expenditure, with both variables standardized. The interaction is small and not statistically significant for average reading achievement and educational poverty, but sizeable and statistically robust for socioeconomic inequality (coefficient = -5.1 ; standard error = 1.778). This indicates that a one-standard-deviation increase in expenditure makes the association between participation and the parental-education gap about 5 points more negative: higher participation is more strongly associated with lower inequality where pre-primary systems are better resourced.

The marginal effects show the same pattern. At low expenditure levels, the association between participation and socioeconomic inequality is close to zero and imprecisely estimated; as expenditure rises, it becomes increasingly negative. This suggests that the gap-closing potential of pre-primary education depends on wider participation being accompanied by adequate investment.

Given the limited data coverage, these findings should be interpreted as exploratory. Still, they reinforce a central implication of the paper: the consequences of pre-primary expansion depend not only on participation levels, but also on the quality and resourcing of provision.

Table 1. Effect of the interaction between participation rate in pre-primary education (PPE) and expenditure per child: results from a meta-multilevel model with random intercepts.

	Average score (mean: 536; sd: 25.73)		Educational poverty (mean: 4.87; sd: 5.30)		Differences between parental ed. groups (mean: 43.20; sd: 9.01)	
	M1	M2	M1	M2	M1	M2
PPE participation rate (standardised)	5.671 (3.186)	6.367* (2.902)	-1.072** (-0.359)	-1.084** (0.353)	-1.455 (1.538)	0.0774 (1.575)
PPE expenditure per child (standardised)		-8.757 (4.508)		0.989 (0.597)		5.782** (2.196)
PPE participation rate # PPE expenditure		-2.506 (3.817)		-0.207 (0.495)		-5.126** (1.778)
Country-level controls (omitted)						

N countries=19
N country-years= 30

5. Discussion and conclusions

This article examined whether the expansion of pre-primary education for children aged 3–5 is associated with later reading outcomes across countries and over time, and whether those associations differ depending on the outcome considered and the level of investment in provision. We suggest that pre-primary education should not be treated as a single undifferentiated equalizer. A more precise way to evaluate its role is to ask what kind of equality-relevant work it performs. The results point to a clear but differentiated pattern. Across

countries and cohorts, higher participation in pre-primary education is consistently associated with higher average reading achievement and lower educational poverty, whereas the association with socioeconomic achievement gaps is weaker and more conditional. In addition, our supplementary analyses suggest that social inequality in access to pre-primary education and unequal returns to attendance tend to persist even in contexts of expanding participation. One plausible explanation is that children from more advantaged families are more likely to attend better-resourced pre-primary settings, but the pattern may also reflect heterogeneous responsiveness to early education itself, insofar as children with more favorable prior learning conditions are better able to capitalize on attendance (Heckman, 2006).

These findings speak directly to a broader debate on the promises and limits of the social investment paradigm. Social investment policies are often expected to achieve several goals at once: to strengthen human capabilities, prevent disadvantage, and weaken the intergenerational transmission of inequality by intervening early in the life course (Morel et al., 2012; Hemerijck, 2017). Our results support part of that expectation, but also qualify it. They suggest that pre-primary expansion is indeed associated with stronger cohort-level competencies and a smaller share of children at the bottom of the performance distribution. In this sense, early investment appears consequential. At the same time, the results are less supportive of a stronger claim often implicit in both policy discourse and academic debate: that expansion by itself is sufficient to loosen the grip of social origin on later educational performance.

The three-function framework developed in the paper helps clarify this distinction. The evidence for a skills-enhancing role is rather clear: countries that expanded pre-primary participation more also tended to display higher later reading achievement among subsequent cohorts, albeit the magnitude of the association is rather modest. Yet, this suggests that expansion is associated with a broad upward shift in the baseline level of competence. The evidence for a floor-raising role points towards a similar direction. Expansion is consistently associated with lower educational poverty, indicating that pre-primary education may reduce the proportion of children who enter and progress through schooling with very weak foundational skills. This matters because the lower tail of the achievement distribution is closely linked to later risks of exclusion, cumulative disadvantage, and constrained life chances (Raudenbush & Eschmann, 2015).

The evidence for the third function, gap closing, is more modest. This is theoretically important. Reducing the dependence of children's outcomes on social origin appears to be a more demanding institutional achievement than improving mean competence or reducing very low performance. Even when pre-primary expansion benefits children broadly, socially advantaged families may remain better positioned to gain access, to secure better-quality provision, to complement institutional inputs with additional investments at home, and to sustain early gains over time (Van Lancker & Ghysels, 2016; Pavolini & Van Lancker, 2018; Kulic et al., 2019). From a stratification perspective, this implies that public expansion can reduce the prevalence of low achievement without fully transforming the mechanisms through which relative

advantage is reproduced. Put differently, early education may alter the lower bound of educational opportunity more readily than the social gradient itself.

This interpretation is reinforced by the exploratory analyses on pre-primary expenditure. Although limited to a smaller subsample, they suggest that the gap-closing potential of pre-primary expansion is stronger where participation is coupled with higher levels of expenditure per child. This points to an important institutional implication: access and quality are analytically intertwined. Participation rates alone do not capture the conditions under which early education is delivered, and the same increase in enrolment can have different consequences depending on whether it is backed by the resources needed to sustain pedagogical quality, staff support, and stable learning environments (OECD, 2019; , 2025; von Suchodoletz et al., 2023). In this respect, the paper contributes to a more institutional reading of social investment: investing early is not only a matter of expanding access, but also of how expansion is organized and resourced.

In sum, our findings suggest that early institutional interventions may be especially effective in shifting the initial distribution of opportunities and in preventing the accumulation of severe disadvantage, but less effective in eliminating the stratified processes through which families convert resources into durable educational advantage over time (Esping-Andersen, 2008; Morel et al., 2012). In that sense, pre-primary expansion may be better understood as a policy that widens the floor of opportunity more than one that fully levels the playing field.

These conclusions should be read in light of some limitations. First, the study is based on repeated cross-sections rather than longitudinal data on the same individuals, which means that the analysis captures associations between cohort-level expansion and later outcomes rather than individual causal effects. Second, the key predictor is derived from retrospective parental reports of pre-primary attendance. Although this measure has important advantages and compares well with external administrative data, it remains subject to some reporting error. Third, even the fixed-effects models cannot rule out all forms of time-varying confounding. Countries that expand pre-primary education may also undergo broader institutional or social changes that are not fully captured by the available controls. Fourth, beyond the fact that our analysis of quality is constrained by limited data availability, our indicator of quality is necessarily partial: expenditure is an important dimension of institutional capacity, but it cannot directly observe the full range of structural and process qualities that shape children's experiences in pre-primary settings.

These limitations point to several avenues for future research. One is to connect the present macro-comparative approach more directly to individual-level causal designs, especially in contexts where high-quality administrative data make it possible to track children from early education into later schooling. Another is to improve the measurement of quality and institutional implementation, moving beyond expenditure to include staff qualifications, child-staff ratios, and more direct indicators of pedagogical practice. Future work could also examine whether the same patterns hold for other domains of achievement, particularly mathematics,

and whether pre-primary expansion matters differently across institutional regimes, policy models, or stages of system development. Finally, the paper raises a broader comparative question that merits further study: under what conditions does early education move from being primarily a means of raising minimum competence levels to becoming a stronger instrument for reducing relative inequalities?

Overall, this study suggests that the expansion of pre-primary education does matter, but not in a uniform way. Pre-primary expansion appears less as a single, all-purpose equalizer than as a policy whose consequences depend on which function we examine and under what institutional conditions expansion takes place. That conclusion is important not only for understanding early childhood education itself, but also for clarifying what social investment policies can realistically be expected to achieve.

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Appendix

A. Details on variables and models

The analyses presented in the paper are based on a two-step multilevel meta-regression approach to estimate the association between standardization and student outcomes.

In the first step, we estimate the three educational outcomes in each country-year sample, based on individual test scores. Table A1 reports model used for each outcome: average achievement is estimated as the constant of an empty regression model; educational poverty is estimated as the probability of scoring below 400, via a linear probability model; socio-economic inequality is estimated via a regression models in which individual test scores are predicted by parental education, net of gender and language spoken at home.

Table A1. First-step estimation: outcomes, estimands, methods, and formulas

Educational outcome	Theoretical estimand	Method	Equation/Formula	Empirical estimand
<i>Average achievement</i>	Mean literacy test score (T)	OLS linear regression	$T_{scy} = \beta_{0,cy} + \varepsilon_{scy}$	Intercept from empty model: $\hat{\beta}_{0,cy} = \bar{T}_{cy}$
<i>Educational poverty</i>	Probability of being low achiever (L)	Linear probability model	$L_{scy} = \pi_{0,cy} + u_{scy}$	Intercept from empty model: $\hat{\pi}_{0,cy} = \bar{L}_{cy}$
<i>Inequality between socioeconomic groups</i>	Gap in test scores between students with at least one tertiary educated parent and the others	OLS linear regression	$T = \beta_{0cy} + \beta_{1c} \text{ParentalEd}_{scy} + \beta_{2cy} \text{Gender}_{scy} + \beta_{3cy} \text{LanguageHome}_{scy} + \varepsilon_{scy}$	Regression coefficient of parental tertiary education dummy: β_{1cy}

Note: s=student, c=country, y=year.

These individual-level regressions are run separately for each country-year, computing standard errors as clustered at the school level. To account for the complex survey design, the estimates are computed using and combining the five plausible values. Finally, we incorporate country-level weights.

In the second step, the coefficients estimated in step one (the five educational outcomes) are treated as dependent variables in multilevel linear models with random effects. The key predictor is the national rate of pre-primary education (PPE) attendance, and the units of analysis are country-years (level 2), nested within countries (level 3). This multilevel structure of the model allows us to account for the potential dependence of effect sizes within countries. The sampling variance from step one is included through the stored standard errors, so more precise country-year estimates receive greater weight in the estimation. In the simplest model specification, random intercepts are modeled at both levels. The second-step model is therefore expressed as follows:

$$\hat{\theta}_{cy} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{PPE_rate}_{cy} + u_c + u_{cy} + \hat{\varepsilon}_{scy}$$

Where $\hat{\theta}_{cy}$ is the estimated scores/coefficients from the first step of the analysis; PPE_rate is the main time-varying macro-variable of interest and has a specific value for each country-year unit; u_{cy} is a country-year level random intercept (level 2), u_j is country-level random intercept (level 3), $\hat{\varepsilon}_{scy}$ is the residual error term derived from the first-step estimates.

In a second model specification, we include the country-level control variables such as the proportion of tertiary educated adults in the country, the proportion of foreign-born population, the proportion of urban population, the Human Development Index, the GINI coefficient, public expenditure on primary education, the share of students enrolled in private primary schools. Table A2 report definitions and sources for each country-level control variables. In a third model specification, we disentangle the within from the between-country variation by further including country fixed-effects. This third model specification also allows us to mitigate the influence of time-invariant country-specific unobservables.

Finally, the models assessing the association between PPE rate and the educational outcomes at different levels of PPE quality include the interaction between PPE attendance rate and PPE expenditure per child, standardized.

Table A2. Definitions and sources of country-level control variables and moderator.

	Definition	Source	Period of availability*
Tertiary educated population	Percentage of of adults (25-64 y.o.) with tertiary education	Barro and Lee (2015); Lee and Lee (2016). Retrieved from: https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/share-of-the-population-with-completed-tertiary-education	2001-2021
Foreign born population	Share of the population that was born in another country	United Nations Population Division, via World Bank. https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/migrant-stock-share	2001-2021
Urban population	Share of the population living in cities and metropolitan areas	United Nations Population Division, via World Bank. Retrieved from: https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/share-of-population-urban	2001-2021
HDI	Human Development Index (0-1)	UNDP, Human Development Report (2024) with minor processing by Our World in Data. https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/human-development-index	2001-2021
GINI index	Gini Index (0-1)	World Bank Poverty and Inequality Platform (2024). Retrieved from: https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/economic-inequality-gini-index	2001-2021
Expenditure for primary education	Government expenditure per student, primary education (% of GDP per capita)	World Bank Open Data. https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.XPD.PRIM.PC.ZS	Available for the years 2001–2016 only; 2021 value imputed by linear extrapolation based on data for 1960–2019

Private schools	Percentage of students enrolled in private schools at the primary level	World Bank Open Data. https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.PRM.PRIV.ZS	2001-2021
Pre-primary expenditure	expenditure per full-time equivalent student, in US dollars, current prices	OECD data explorer https://data-explorer.oecd.org	2016-2021**

* For each variable, missing observations for individual country-years were imputed using all available data for the corresponding country, including observations outside the 2001–2021 period considered in this paper. Imputation was performed using linear interpolation and extrapolation.

** For expenditure per child, the years reported correspond to the PIRLS survey year for each cohort; the underlying expenditure data refer to the year four years earlier, when that cohort was of age to attend the final year of pre-primary education.

B. Descriptive statistics

Table B1. Sample description: total available observations by country and year

	2001	2006	2011	2016	2021	Total
Austria	.	4,825	4,454	4,090	4,344	17,713
Azerbaijan	.	.	4,576	5,668	4,235	14,479
Belgium. Flemish	.	4,334	.	4,615	4,219	13,168
Belgium. French	.	4,089	3,388	4,033	3,309	14,819
Bulgaria	3,303	3,703	5,136	4,206	3,903	20,251
Canada	6,864	.	18,816	14,762	.	40,442
Colombia	4,666	.	3,823	.	.	8,489
Czech Republic	2,666	.	4,419	5,281	5,684	18,050
Denmark	.	3,741	4,333	3,305	4,417	15,796
Finland	.	.	4,425	4,540	6,419	15,384
France	3,175	4,062	4,119	4,204	4,509	20,069
Georgia	.	4,226	4,631	5,455	.	14,312
Germany	.	6,851	3,200	2,813	.	12,864
Hong Kong SAR	4,762	4,572	3,599	3,256	3,694	19,883
Hungary	4,462	3,707	4,919	4,403	.	17,491
Indonesia	.	4,492	4,519	.	.	9,011
Ireland	.	.	4,267	4,208	.	8,475
Islamic Rep. of Iran	7,192	5,301	5,658	4,297	5,585	28,033
Israel	.	.	3,280	3,471	.	6,751
Italy	3,414	3,429	3,876	3,615	4,940	19,274
Latvia	2,878	3,912	.	3,915	.	10,705
Lithuania	2,508	4,549	4,422	3,705	.	15,184
Macao SAR	.	.	.	3,995	4,972	8,967
Moldova	3,453	3,867	.	.	.	7,320
Morocco	.	3,146	7,021	5,080	.	15,247
Norway	3,137	3,531	2,915	4,022	.	13,605
Oman	.	.	9,053	8,841	4,960	22,854
Poland	.	4,544	4,891	4,281	3,896	17,612
Portugal	.	.	3,876	4,460	5,696	14,032
Qatar	.	.	3,635	7,616	.	11,251
Republic of North M..	.	3,763	.	.	2,665	6,428
Romania	3,508	4,157	4,507	.	.	12,172
Russian Federation	1,469	4,677	4,418	4,524	4,911	19,999
Saudi Arabia	.	.	4,366	4,438	.	8,804
Singapore	6,881	6,249	6,196	6,318	5,954	31,598
Slovak Republic	3,680	5,202	5,480	5,274	4,136	23,772
Slovenia	.	.	.	4,292	4,532	8,824
Spain	.	.	7,957	13,345	7,442	28,744
Sweden	5,483	4,062	3,974	3,839	.	17,358
Taipei Chinese	.	4,460	4,243	4,245	5,422	18,370
Trinidad and Tobago	.	3,489	3,495	3,546	.	10,530
Turkiye	4,899	.	.	.	5,551	10,450
United Arab Emirates	.	.	13,171	14,711	.	27,882
Total	78,400	116,940	189,058	196,669	115,395	696,462

NOTE: the valid sample sizes are slightly smaller for the models of inter-group inequalities because individual-level control variables (gender, parental education, or language spoken at home) are unavailable for some respondents. Country-year samples were excluded if the dependent variable (pre-primary education attendance) or any individual-level control variable was missing for more than 30% of respondents. Countries with data available for fewer than two years were also excluded.

Table B2. Descriptive statistics for the three educational outcomes.

	2001	2006	2011	2016	2021
(a) average reading score	514.63	508.67	506.06	519.71	517.49
(b) educational poverty (%)	10.30	12.53	13.33	10.66	10.13
(c) diff. between parental educ. groups (high vs low)	43.33	49.20	47.69	45.67	45.48

Figure B1. Pre-primary participation rates by country and in each year

Fig. B2. Proportion of variance of PPE participation rate absorbed by country fixed effects

Figure B3. Comparison between participation rates estimated on PIRLS data and administrative data on gross enrollment rate in pre-primary education collected (linear correlation: 0.85)

- PIRLS data (95% CI)
- ◆ Administrative data (World Bank database)

NOTE: administrative data are collected by UNESCO and are available on the World Bank Databank: <https://databank.worldbank.org/metadataglossary/world-development-indicators/series/SE.PRE.ENRR>

Table B3. Descriptive statistics for the main predictor, the country-level controls and the moderator.

		Mean	SD	Min	Max	N*
Predictor	Share of students having attended ECEC (%)	88.36	14.67	24.29	100.00	143
Country-level controls	Tertiary educated population (%)	25.97	13.32	5.40	70.12	132
	Foreign born population (%)	0.85	0.08	0.58	0.96	143
	Urban population (%)	12.61	3.78	2.02	24.42	139
	HDI (0-1)	0.33	0.06	0.24	0.57	137
	GINI index (0-1)	14.02	19.83	0.00	97.81	124
	Expenditure on primary education	14.19	17.09	0.04	84.45	120
	Private schools (%)	73.99	15.10	42.74	100.00	139
Moderator	Pre-primary expenditure (original variable)	7545	2624	3997	14948	30
	Pre-primary expenditure (standard. variable)	0	1	-1.35	2.82	30

* N refers to the number of country-year units. Some of the country-level controls are unavailable for some countries. The moderator is only available in European countries.

Table B4. Correlation between country-level control variables.

	Tertiary educated	Foreign born pop.	Urban pop.	HDI	GINI index	Exp. on primary ed.	Private schools
Tertiary educated pop.	1.00						
Foreign born pop.	0.55	1.00					
Urban pop.	0.64	0.52	1.00				
HDI	0.67	0.68	0.58	1.00			
GINI index	-0.29	-0.26	-0.15	-0.59	1.00		
Exp. on primary educ.	0.09	0.10	0.05	0.15	-0.11	1.00	
Private schools	0.17	0.26	0.42	0.12	-0.12	0.06	1.00

Figure B3. Linear correlation between pre-primary participation rate and each of the time-varying country-level controls. Each dot represents one country-year unit.

Figure B4. Correlations between pre-primary participation rate and the five educational outcomes

C. Robustness checks

Figure C1. Regression results on socioeconomic inequality estimated as a function of maternal education only

Figure C2. Correlations between pre-primary participation rate (after natural logarithmic transformation of the variable) and the five educational outcomes.

Figure C3. Regression results using a natural logarithmic transformation of the variable on pre-primary participation rate.

Figure C4. Regression results on the analytical sample restricted to country-year units with no missing value in every country-level control variable

